

Comprehensive Analysis of Ocular Injuries in Road Traffic Accidents in a Tertiary Care Setting

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Abstract:

Introduction: Road traffic accidents (RTAs) are a major public health concern worldwide, often resulting in significant ocular trauma. This study provides a thorough examination of ocular injuries sustained in RTAs, focusing on gender differences, injury patterns, and visual acuity outcomes in a tertiary care setting.

Materials and Methods: A prospective cross-sectional study was conducted at the ophthalmology department of Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Center. Data were collected from RTA patients with ocular injuries over a six-month period.

Demographic information, injury characteristics, and visual acuity measurements were obtained through structured questionnaires and clinical examinations.

Results: Analysis of 70 eyes revealed a predominance of males, with a wide range of ocular injuries observed. Common manifestations included edema, ecchymosis, subconjunctival hemorrhage, and orbital fractures. Visual acuity varied among patients, with a notable proportion experiencing impaired vision ranging from normal to severe.

Conclusion: Ocular injuries in RTAs pose significant challenges in terms of morbidity and visual impairment. Understanding the interplay between gender, injury patterns, and visual outcomes is crucial for implementing targeted interventions and improving patient outcomes. By addressing risk factors and enhancing safety measures, healthcare providers can mitigate the impact of ocular trauma and preserve vision in affected individuals.

Keywords: Ocular injuries, Road traffic accidents, Gender disparity, Injury patterns, Visual acuity, Tertiary care setting.

Introduction:

Road traffic accidents (RTAs) stand as a predominant cause of polytrauma, casting a significant shadow over public health globally. Within this grim statistic lies a particularly alarming reality: ocular trauma emerges as a silent yet profound contributor to the burden of injury, with repercussions echoing across millions of lives worldwide. This silent assailant frequently seizes the spotlight as a principal cause of unilateral vision loss, a stark reality that often hits hardest in developing nations. [1,2]

In the intricate tapestry of ocular injuries sustained in RTAs, no part of the eye remains unscathed. From the delicate architecture of the eyelids to the intricate network of the optic nerve, the spectrum of potential damage is vast and unforgiving. The repercussions ripple through every layer of ocular anatomy, sparing none: from the superficial conjunctiva to the depths of the vitreous, and even the structural integrity of the globe itself.[3]

Every year, more than 55 million people worldwide suffer eye injuries. Among them, 2.3 million people have both eyes affected, while a staggering 19 million people experience damage unilaterally. This accounts to ocular trauma as the most common cause of preventable blindness. The number of road traffic accidents (RTAs) is increasing nowadays, resulting in serious eye injuries. This results in serious social and financial issues which includes loss of work, longer duration hospital stays, ongoing check-ups, and needing help to see better again. Eye injuries also brings a lot of emotional stress.[4-9]

Ocular trauma, like injuries to the eyes from accidents, is more than just physical harm. It can also lead to permanent blindness, which is very serious. These injuries, especially from road accidents, not only affect one eye but can also have a big impact on social and economic well being. We need to have better understanding of the causes to enhance a better prevention, treatment and rehabilitative measures. Hence this study was planned in a tertiary care set up to understand the nature of Ocular injuries.

Materials and Methods:

A prospective cross-sectional study was conducted at the ophthalmology department of Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Center, following approval from the ethical committee (Ref No: 786/TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2023 -IEC No:078). The study period spanned from August 2023 to January 2024, during which all road traffic accident patients with ocular injuries were included after obtaining informed and written consent

either from the conscious patient or their attendant. Re-consent was obtained from patients upon regaining consciousness.

A structured questionnaire, pretested and predesigned, was utilized to collect information on the type of vehicle involved, accident time, and location. Symptoms and signs following the injury were recorded, followed by a torch light examination. Visual acuity assessment was performed using Snellen's chart based on the patient's condition, followed by slit-lamp examination for ambulatory patients to evaluate the anterior segment. Intraocular pressure (IOP) was measured using non-contact tonometry, with gonioscopy performed if necessary.

Direct and indirect ophthalmoscopy were conducted to evaluate the posterior segment, and any abnormalities were noted. Radiological investigations were performed if indicated. B-scan ultrasonography was carried out for cases with media haziness or opacities. Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically frequencies and percentages, to present the study findings.

Results:

In the study, a total of 70 eyes were examined, with 82.85% (58 eyes) belonging to males and the remaining 17.15% (12 eyes) to females. The mean age of the participants was 36.56 years with a standard deviation of 6.83 years, ranging from 7 to 66 years. Approximately 80% of the study population fell between the ages of 21 to 50 years, with half of them (50%) between 21 to 40 years. The majority of injuries (72.86%) occurred while using two-wheelers, followed by 18.57% while using four-wheelers, and the remaining 8.57% while walking on the road.

All 70 eyes (100%) exhibited edema. Ecchymosis was observed in 60% (42 eyes), subconjunctival hemorrhage in 50% (35 eyes), lateral wall fracture in 25.71% (18 eyes), medial wall fracture in 18.57% (13 eyes), and congestion in 17.14% (12 eyes). Traumatic

optic neuropathy was found in 11.43% of cases. Additionally, lid tear, chemosis, fracture roof, muscle entrapment, corneal tear, traumatic cataract, and Berlin's edema were present in 7.14%, 8.57%, 5.71%, 4.29%, 1.43%, 1.43%, and 1.43% of cases, respectively.(Table 1)

Table 1: Ocular Manifestations after RTA

	No. of cases	Percentage
Edema	70	100.00
Ecchymosis	42	60.00
Lid tear	5	7.14
SCH	35	50.00
Chemosis	6	8.57
Congestion	12	17.14
Corneal tear	1	1.43
Traumatic cataract	1	1.43
Subluxation of lens	0	0.00
Berlins edema	1	1.43
Traumatic optic neuropathy	8	11.43
Lateral wall fracture	18	25.71
Medial fracture	13	18.57
Fracture of roof	4	5.71
Combined fracture	7	10.00
Muscle entrapment	3	4.29

Regarding visual acuity assessment, 20% (14) had normal vision, while 51.43% (36) had vision between 6/9 to 6/12. Another 22.86% had visual acuity between 6/18 to 6/36, and approximately 3% had vision ranging from 6/60 to 1/60. Additionally, 1.43% of participants had hand motion (HM) vision, and another 1.43% had no perception of light (No PL).(Table 2)

Table 2 : Visual acuity during presentation

Vision	No. of cases	Percentage
6/6	14	20.00
6/9 - 6/12	36	51.43
6/18 – 6//36	16	22.86
6/60 – 1/60	2	2.86
CFCF	0	0.00
HM	1	1.43
PL	0	0.00
No PL	1	1.43

Discussion:

Conducted at a tertiary care medical college in South India, this study aimed to investigate ocular manifestations resulting from road traffic accidents. Examining a total of 70 eyes, our findings revealed a striking predominance of males, accounting for more than four-fifths of the study participants. This observation aligns with numerous prior studies, which consistently indicate that men are more prone to ocular injuries compared to women.

The higher susceptibility of men to ocular injuries can likely be attributed to various factors such as lifestyle, occupation, and their generally more active involvement in community

activities. Men often engage in occupations or activities that expose them to higher risks of trauma, such as driving vehicles or participating in outdoor sports. Additionally, societal roles and expectations may influence men to take on more physically demanding tasks, further increasing their likelihood of encountering ocular injuries.

The cultural and societal context in South India may also contribute to this gender disparity in ocular injuries. Traditional gender roles and expectations may lead to differences in exposure to risk factors between men and women. For example, men may be more likely to engage in activities like driving or manual labor, which inherently carry a higher risk of ocular trauma.

Understanding these gender differences in ocular injury susceptibility is crucial for developing targeted prevention strategies and providing appropriate medical care. By recognizing the specific risk factors and behaviors associated with ocular injuries in different demographic groups, healthcare professionals can better educate patients and implement measures to mitigate these risks, ultimately reducing the burden of ocular trauma in the community.[10-17]

A study conducted in Nigeria attributes the higher occurrence of ocular injuries among males to their greater mobility and engagement in high-risk behaviors like reckless driving, leading to increased involvement in road traffic accidents (RTAs).¹⁸ Conversely, females are less susceptible to RTA-related ocular injuries due to their tendency to stay at home and undertake less hazardous jobs.[19]

Around one-third of individuals in the study, aged between 21 to 30 years and 41 to 50 years, were affected by ocular injuries. Alam et al.[18] from India reported a higher incidence among the 21 to 30 years age group, whereas Muralidhar et al.[2] from South India observed a higher incidence in the 41 to 50 years age group. Vulnerability to ocular trauma is more prevalent in young adults and the productive age group, with a decrease observed in the elderly and dependent age groups.[6,20,21]

Nearly three-fourths of the injuries were attributed to two-wheeler accidents, consistent with findings from other studies. Ocular manifestations and visual impairments observed in the study align with those reported in studies conducted in various parts of India.[2,4,6,11,14-16,19,20] Orbital fracture appears to be an independent risk factor for a poor prognosis in RTA-related eye injuries. Ruptured globe with orbital fractures represents a severe type of eye injury that may carry a worse prognosis.[6]The utilization of protective helmets and eyewear could have substantially reduced the incidence of eye injuries.[22]

Fig 1: Distribution of study population according to age

Conclusion:

Our study underscores the significant gender disparity in ocular injuries resulting from road traffic accidents, with men being more susceptible due to various lifestyle factors and societal expectations. Understanding these differences is pivotal for crafting targeted prevention strategies and delivering tailored medical care. Implementing measures such as promoting the use of protective gear like helmets and eyewear, especially among vulnerable groups such as young adults involved in two-wheeler accidents, is crucial for reducing the burden of ocular trauma. Additionally, raising awareness about the importance of safe driving practices and advocating for stricter enforcement of traffic regulations can contribute to mitigating the occurrence of RTA-related ocular injuries. By addressing these factors comprehensively, we can work towards alleviating the impact of ocular trauma and preserving vision in our communities.

Declarations

Funding: No funding source

Conflict of interest: None declared

Ethical approval: This study was registered with Institutional Human Ethical Committee.

References

1. JD McCann S Seiff Traumatic neuropathies of the optic nerve, optic chiasm, and ocular motor nerves *Curr Opin Ophthalmol* 1994;5(6):1010-1019. doi:10.1097/00055735-199412000-00002
2. Muralidhar P, Chowdary NL. Ocular manifestations in road traffic accidents: a study done at a medical college hospital in South India. *Int J Contemporary Med Res.* 2016;3(8):2337-9
3. D J Thurman L Jeppson C L Burnett Surveillance of traumatic brain injury in Utah *West J Med* 1996;165:1926.
4. Sree KV, Reddy BK. A Clinical Study of Ocular Injuries in Road Traffic Accident Patients in a Tertiary Care Hospital. *J Dental Med Sci.* 2019;18(2):24-7.
5. Qayum S, Anjum R, Garg P. Epidemiological pattern of ocular trauma in a tertiary hospital of northern India. *Int J Biomed Res.* 2016;7(7):420-22.
6. Maurya RP, Srivastav T, Singh V, Mishra C, Al-Mujaini A. The epidemiology of ocular trauma in Northern India: A teaching hospital study. *Oman J Ophthalmol.* 2019;12(2):78–83. doi:10.4103/ojo.ojo_149_2018.
7. Négrel AD, Thylefors B. The global impact of eye injuries. *Ophthalmic Epidemiol.* 1998;5(3):143–69. doi:10.1076/oep.5.3.143.8364
8. FHuelke D, O'DAY J, Barhydt W. Ocular Injuries in Automobile Crashes. *J Trauma.* 1982;22(1):50–9. doi:10.1097/00005373-198201000-00009.
9. Huelke DF, Grabb WC, Dingman RO. Facial injuries in automobile accidents. In *Proceedings, American association for automotive medicine, Louisville; 1964.*

10. Jamal BT, Pfahler SM, Lane KA, Bilyk JR, Pribitkin EA, Diecidue RJ et al. Ophthalmic injuries in patients with zygomaticomaxillary complex fractures requiring surgical repair. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2009;67(5):986-9.
11. Mittal G, Singh N, Suvarana S, Mittal SR. A prospective study on ophthalmic injuries related to maxillofacial trauma in Indian population. *Natl J Maxillofac Surg.* 2012;3(2):152-8.
12. Al-Qurainy IA, Stassen LF, Dutton GN, Moos KF, El-Attar A. The characteristics of midfacial fractures and the association with ocular injury: a prospective study. *Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 1991;29(5):291-301.
13. Riaz N, Chatha AA, Warraich RA, Hanif S, Chinar KA, Khan SR. Ophthalmic injuries in orbito zygomatic fractures. *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak.* 2014;24(9):649-52.
14. Ansari MH. Blindness after facial fractures: a 19-year retrospective study. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2005;63(2):229- 37.
15. Kumar J, Singh VP, Chaubey P, Kumar V. Ocular injuries in road traffic accidents (RTA). *J Dent Med Sci.* 2017;16(11):55–60.
16. Arora AS, Bhargava G, Chauhan A. Ocular trauma in road traffic accidents: Experience at Mathra Das Hospital. *Rajasthan J Ophthalmol.* 2011;3:1–3.
17. Johnston PB, Armstrong MF. Eye injuries in Northern Ireland two years after seat belt legislation. *Br J Ophthalmol.* 1986;70(6):460–2.
18. Oluyemi F. Epidemiology of penetrating eye injury in Ibadan: A 10-year hospital-based review. *Middle East African journal of ophthalmology.* 2011;18(2):159.
19. Namala B, Rao KS, Gurunadh V. Road Accidents and Ocular Injuries. *IP Journal of Surgery and Allied Sciences.* 2019;1(1):13-6.

20. Alam J, Bhattacharjya H, Roy A, Das M. Epidemiology and outcome of ocular trauma among the road traffic accident cases attending a tertiary care hospital in Tripura. *Int J Med Sci Public Health*. 2014;3(4):422–4.
21. Frederick M, Kumaresan V, Anuradha P. A clinical study on types of ocular injuries following road traffic accidents in a tertiary health care hospital in Chennai, Tamil Nadu. *Int J Adv Med* 2023;10:67-72.
22. Oladejo OJ, Ademola-Popoola, Nyamngee A, Owoeye F. Causation, Types and Outcome of Road Traffic – related Ocular Injury in University of Llorin, Kwara, Nigeria. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*. 2024 Apr, Vol-18(4): NC12-NC15.